

Christianity in Byzantium: between the end of Iconoclasm and the Schism

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Entry tags: Religious Group, Christianity

The Council of Constantinople that the Byzantine regent Theodora summoned in 843 convened to refute iconoclasm and restore the worship and the veneration of the Holy Icons, marking the end of Iconoclasm, which caused several serious problems to the Byzantine empire in both religious and political level. However, albeit the period after iconoclasm was generally peaceful, it was not entirely tranquil, since the iconoclastic controversy left behind a legacy of factions. Patriarch Methodius I (843-847) accommodated former iconoclasts in the Church, provided that they renounce their heretic views. Methodius's policy met strong opposition by the monks of the Studios monastery in Constantinople, many of which were excommunicated by Methodius before his death in 847. An intense struggle for succession has begun until Empress Theodora appointed St. Ignatius, the son of the Emperor Michael I Rangabe and opponent of Iconoclasm, to succeed Methodios. St. Ignatius was fervently accused by his enemies that, since he had not been elected in a synod and subsequently confirmed by the Emperor, but he was being appointed by the Empress Theodora, he was not a legitimate patriarch. Furthermore, St. Ignatius soon became involved in the conflict between the monks of the Stoudion monastery and the moderates in the Church. This dispute was about whether to depose clergymen who had cooperated with iconoclast policies in the past or not. Ignatius took the side of the conservative Stoudite monks and deposed the archbishop of Syracuse, Gregory Asbestos (844-880), the leader of the moderate party. Asbestos protested in 853 to Pope Leo IV (847-855) seeking a redress. Thus, a period of friction in relations between the Church of Rome and that of Constantinople had begun: Asbestos and several other bishops had been condemned in a synod called by St. Ignatius without papal consent. These events were the beginning for the so-called Photian schism. The schism was initially caused due to political reasons. Michael III (the so-called Drunkard) became emperor at a young age, while his mother Theodora served as regent. His uncle Bardas, Theodora's brother, was an influential advisor. However, he found a fervent critic in the face of St. Ignatius: Bardas was accused of committing incest with his daughter-in-law, therefore St. Ignatius publicly denied him the Eucharist in the Hagia Sophia. Consequently, St. Ignatius lost support and he was forced to resign in 858. He was replaced by the layman Photius. Photius became a monk on December 20, 858 and on the following four days was successively ordained lector, sub-deacon, deacon and priest. He was made patriarch on Christmas day. St. Ignatius's supporters however sought the aid of Pope Nicholas I (858-867). The Pope was angered by Byzantine missions among the Bulgars, whom he regarded as belonging to his jurisdiction. Nicholas wrote to the Bulgarians accusing the Greeks and Photius replied by accusing the Western Church of heretically altering the creed in saying that the Holy Spirit proceeds from the Father and from the Son (Filioque). He declared Pope Nicholas deposed in 867. When the new emperor, Basil I the founder of the Macedonian dynasty, rose to the Byzantine throne, he reinstated St. Ignatius while Pope Nicholas's successor (869) Adrian II, condemned Photius. But when St. Ignatius passed away, Photius quietly became patriarch again. Hence a schism occurred, which is called the Photian schism. The schism was mostly about whether the Church of Rome possessed monarchical power of jurisdiction over all churches, or whether it was the senior of the five Patriarchates and therefore could not canonically interfere with the internal affairs of another Patriarchate. The mutual distrust shown in the time of Photius erupted again in the middle of the 11th century, after papal enforcement of Latin customs upon Greeks in southern Italy. The patriarch of Constantinople, Michael Cerularius (1043 - 1059), closed Latin churches in Constantinople as a reprisal. Cerularius quarreled with Pope Leo IX over church practices in which the Roman Church differed from Constantinople, particularly the use of unleavened bread in the Eucharist. Dissenting opinions were also

exchanged over other theological and cultural issues, ranging from the issue of papal supremacy in the Church to the filioque clause and other disagreements between the patriarchates. Cardinal Humbert of Silva Candida (or Humbert of Moyenmoutier) came from Italy to protest, was accorded an icy reception, and left a bull of excommunication (July 16, 1054) on the altar of the great church of Hagia Sophia. The bull anathematized (condemned) Michael Cerularius, the Greek doctrine of the Holy Spirit, the marriage of Greek priests, and the Greek use of leavened bread for the Eucharist. These events caused the East-West Schism and led to the end of the alliance between the Byzantine emperors and the Popes. Later Popes allied with the Normans against the Byzantine Empire.

Date Range: 843 CE - 1054 CE

Region: Byzantine Empire.

Region tags: Eastern Mediterranean, Greece, Eastern Europe, Byzantium, Cyprus, Dalmatia

The Byzantine Empire, ca 1025.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Mark Whittow, (1996), *The Making of Byzantium, 600–1025*, University of California Press, ISBN 0-520-20496-4
- Source 2: Francis Dvornik, *The Photian schism. History and Legend*, Cambridge University Press, Cambridge 1948
- Source 3: *The Homilies of Photius, Patriarch of Constantinople: English Translation, Introduction and Commentary* by Cyril Mango, Wipf and Stock Publishers, 2018

Reference: Signes-Codoñer, Juan , and Jeffrey Michael Featherstone. *Chronographiae Quae Theophanis Continuati Nomine Fertur Libri I-IV. Corpus Fontium Historiae Byzantinae – Series Berolinensis 53*. Berlin, Boston: De Gruyter, 2015. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1515/9781614515043>.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.oca.org/orthodoxy/the-orthodox-faith/church-history/ninth-century/the-end-of-iconoclasm>
- Source 1 Description: The end of Iconoclasm
- Source 2 URL: <https://www.coe.int/en/web/cultural-routes/cyril-and-methodius-route>
- Source 2 Description: Cyril and Methodius Route
- Source 3 URL: <https://www.newadvent.org/cathen/04592a.htm>
- Source 3 Description: Sts. Cyril and Methodius

Notes: *The Greek Schism and its Political Implications: <https://www.doaks.org/research/library-archives/dumbarton-oaks-archives/collections/historical-papers/henri-gregoire-papers/the-greek-schism-and-its-political-implications> *Great Schism of the Church 1054 AD (Church History): <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=trMsytBdawc> *The Schism, BBC Radio: <https://www.bbc.co.uk/programmes/p0054921>

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

– Source 1 URL: <https://www.perseus.tufts.edu/hopper/text?doc=Perseus%3Atext%3A2008.01.0472>

– Source 1 Description: Greek Anthology

– Source 2 URL: <https://digi.ub.uni-heidelberg.de/diglit/cpgraec23/0011/image.info>

– Source 2 Description: Anthologia Palatina, digitized manuscript, University of Heidelberg

– Source 3 URL: https://www.oodegr.com/oode/dogma/kanones/synodiko_or8odoksias_1.htm

– Source 3 Description: The Synodikon of Orthodoxy

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Is the cultural contact competitive:

– Yes

Notes: For example, the brothers Cyril and Methodius had great success among Slavic people, mainly for using the native language rather than Latin or Greek. In Great Moravia, they encountered missionaries from East Francia, representing the western or Latin branch of the Church, more particularly representing the Carolingian Empire, which was committed to both linguistic and cultural uniformity. The Latin (or Western) missionaries insisted on the use of the Latin liturgy, and they regarded Moravia and the Slavic peoples as part of their rightful mission field. Friction developed and the two brothers decided to visit Rome in order to see the Pope and seek a solution that would avoid quarreling between missionaries. That because, by that time, the mission of the two Byzantines in Moravia had become the focus of a dispute with Archbishop Adalwin of Salzburg and Bishop Ermanrich of Passau, who both claimed ecclesiastical control of the same territory and wished to use the Latin liturgy exclusively. Furthermore, the main issue about the so-called Photian schism was whether Rome possessed monarchical power of jurisdiction over all churches, or whether the Church of Rome was the senior among the five Patriarchates, as Photius and the Greeks thought, and therefore could not canonically interfere with the internal affairs of another Patriarchate. The mutual distrust shown in the time of Photius erupted again in the middle of the 11th century after papal enforcement of Latin customs upon Greeks in southern Italy. The patriarch of Constantinople, Michael Cerularius, closed Latin churches in Constantinople as a reprisal. Cardinal Humbert who travelled from Italy to Constantinople to protest, left a bull of excommunication (July of 1054) on the altar of the great church of Hagia Sophia. The bull anathematized Michael Cerularius, the Greek doctrine of the Holy Spirit, the marriage of Greek priests, and the Greek use of leavened bread for the Eucharist.

Reference: Wurster, Herbert Wilhelm . *Das Bistum Passau Und Seine Geschichte*. 4 Bände. Strasbourg: Editions du Signe, 1994.

Reference: Dvornik, Francis . *The Photian Schism. History and Legend*. Cambridge : Cambridge University Press, 1948. <http://macedonia.kroraina.com/en/fdps/index.htm>.

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– No

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– Yes

Notes: In 843, the Empress Theodora, as regent to her son Michael III, launched a major persecution against the Paulicians throughout Asia Minor. The Emperor Basil I, founder of the Macedonian dynasty, waged war against the heretical Paulicians, centered on the small city of Tephrike on the upper Euphrates, which was the seat of the separate principality that the heretics had founded. The heresy of Paulicians rebelled, allied with the Arabs and raided as far as Nicaea, sacking Ephesus. The Byzantine army defeated the Paulicians in 872, at the battle of Bathys Ryax, where the Paulican leader Chrysocheir, died. The outcome of the battle led to the definite subjection of the Paulican state. Furthermore, the Emperor Basil pursued an active policy to restore the Empire's power in the West. He allied with the Holy Roman Emperor Louis II against the Arabs and sent a fleet of ships to clear the Adriatic Sea of their raids. With Byzantine help, Louis II captured Bari from the Arabs in 871. The city eventually became Byzantine territory in 876.

Reference: Garsoïan, Nina G. *The Paulician Heresy: A Study of the Origin and Development of Paulicianism in Armenia and the Eastern Provinces of the Byzantine Empire.* Paris: Mouton, 1967.

Reference: Haldon, John. *The Byzantine Wars: Battles and Campaigns of the Byzantine Era.* Gloucestershire: Tempus, 2001.

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– Yes

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Yes

↳ Assigned at birth (membership is default for this society):

– Yes

↳ Assigned by personal choice:

– Yes

↳ Assigned by class:

– No

↳ Assigned at a specific age:

– No

↳ Assigned by gender:

– No

↳ Assigned by participation in a particular ritual:

– No

↳ Assigned by some other factor:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– Yes

Notes: In 862, when Prince Rostislav of Great Moravia asked the Byzantines to send missionaries, the emperor Michael III and the patriarch Photius named Cyril and Methodius. These latter were brothers from Thessaloniki, already experienced in missionary work. They started their work among the Slavs in 863, using Slavonic in the liturgy. They translated the Bible into the language later known as Old Church Slavonic, or Old Bulgarian, and invented the Glagolitic alphabet, a Slavic alphabet based on Greek characters that in its final Cyrillic form is still in use as the alphabet for modern Russian and a number of other Slavic languages. Because the two brothers Christianized the Danubian Slavs and deeply influenced the religious and cultural development of all Slavic peoples they are called “the Apostles of the Slavs.”

Reference: Komatina,, Predrag. “the Church in Serbia at the Time of Cyrilo-methodian Mission in Moravia”. In *Cyril and Methodius: Byzantium and the World of the Slavs, 711-18*. Thessaloniki: Dimos, 2015.

Reference: Whittow, Mark. *The Making of Orthodox Byzantium, 600-1025*. Macmillan Education UK, 1996. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-349-24765-3>.

Reference: Betti,, Maddalena. *The Making of Christian Moravia (858-882): Papal Power and Political Reality*. Leiden-Boston: Brill, 2013.

Reference: Curta,, Florin. *Eastern Europe in the Middle Ages (500-1300)*. Leiden, Boston: Brill, 2019.

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for religious professionals:

– No

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for all adherents:

– No

↳ Is missionary work mandated for religious professionals:

– No

Notes: Nevertheless, various missions were carried out during the period under investigation. The two brothers Cyril and Methodius worked for the conversion of the Khazars, Turkic-speaking tribes, northeast of the Black Sea in 860. Earlier, since Cyril knew both Arabic and Hebrew, he was sent to the Abbasid caliph al-Mutawakkil to discuss the doctrine of the Holy Trinity with Arab theologians and to improve relations between the Caliphate and the Byzantine Empire.

Reference: Κραλίδης, Απόστολος. *Οι Χάζαροι Και Το Βυζάντιο. Ιστορική Και Θρησκευολογική Προσέγγιση.* Thessaloniki: Savvalas, 2003.

↳ Is missionary work mandated for all adherents:

– No

↳ Is proselytization coercive:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

↳ Are the priests paid by polity:

– Yes

↳ Is religious infrastructure paid for by the polity:

– Yes

↳ Are the head of the polity and the head of the religion the same figure:

– No

↳ Are political officials equivalent to religious officials:

– No

↳ Is religious observance enforced by the polity:

– No

↳ Polity legal code is roughly coterminous with religious code:

– No

↳ Polity provides preferential economic treatment (e.g. tax, exemption)

– Yes

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Large religious group (with smaller religious groups not officially allowed but in practice tolerated)

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Is there a hierarchy among these leaders:

– Yes

↳ A single leader of a local community:

– Yes

↳ Multiple religious communities each with its own leader, no hierarchy among these leaders:

– No

↳ "Regional" leaders who oversee one or more local leader(s) (e.g. bishops):

– Yes

↳ A single leader for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:

– Yes

↳ A council or group of leaders for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:

– Yes

↳ Estimate how many levels there are in the hierarchy of religious leadership:

– Number of levels [numeric value]: 5

↳ Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:

– No

↳ Are religious leaders chosen:

– No

↳ Are leaders considered fallible:

– Yes

↳ Charges of fallibility made by a leader's own followers:

– Yes

↳ Charges of fallibility made by other leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Charges of fallibility made by a political ruler:

– Yes

↳ Are close followers or disciples of a religious leader required to obediently and unquestionably accept the leader's pronouncements on all matters:

– Field doesn't know

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

↳ Are they oral:

– No

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– I don't know

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

Notes: The integration of monumental art and domed architecture can be found in the churches of Hosios Loukas, situated at a scenic site on the slopes of Mount Helicon. It was founded in the early 10th century AD by the hermit, Venerable Luke of Steiris, whose relics are kept in the monastery to this day. In Nea Moni, built in the mid-11th century, by Byzantine emperor Constantine IX Monomachos and his wife, Empress Zoe in Chios. And Daphni, an eleventh-century Byzantine monastery eleven kilometers northwest of central Athens in the suburb of Chaidari. The aforementioned monuments are all located in Greece and decorated with mosaic icons, as well as with the church of St. Panteleimon at Gorno Nerezi, constructed in 1164 as a foundation of Alexios Angelos, a son of Constantine Angelos, adorned with frescoes. Furthermore, between 1077-1081 Maria Doukaina, the mother-in-law of Alexius I Comnenus, rebuilt the Chora Church as an inscribed cross or quincunx, a popular architectural style of the time. Early in the 12th century, the church suffered a partial collapse, perhaps due to an earthquake.

↳ In the average settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Field doesn't know

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

↳ Tombs:

– Yes

↳ Cemeteries:

– Yes

Notes: <https://www.doaks.org/research/byzantine/project-grants/bourbou-2010-2011>

↳ Temples:

– Yes

↳ Altars:

– Yes

↳ Devotional markers:

– Yes

Reference: Drandaki, Anastasia . "Icons in the Devotional Practices of Byzantium". In *Heaven and Earth: Art of Byzantium from Greek Collections*, Exh. Cat. The National Gallery of Art, Washington and the J.P. Getty Museum, Los Angeles, 109-14. Athens, 2013.

↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:

– Yes

Notes: An example is the Kainourgion, a palatine hall built by Emperor Basil I from 867-886. Covered in mosaics to glorify the Macedonian dynasty, the Kainourgion depicted Basil's military victories and functioned as an imperial palace with audience chamber, a dining room, and connected bedrooms.

Reference: Alexander, Paul. "The Strength of Empire and Capital as Seen Through Byzantine Eyes". *Speculum* 37, no. 3 (1962): 339-57. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.2307/2852356>.

↳ Other type of religious monumental architecture:

– Field doesn't know

Is iconography present:

– Yes

Notes: After iconoclasm, new churches continued to elaborate on the domed architecture developed in the pre-Iconoclastic period, though on a smaller scale. With the end of Iconoclasm and affirmation of icons, art and architecture developed in tandem: new churches were built to accommodate extensive decoration with images, and mosaics and frescoes were deployed to fit the many curved and angled surfaces of church interiors.

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

– At home

– Only religious public space

– Some public spaces

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– Yes

Reference: Barber, Charles. "From Image into Art: Art After Byzantine Iconoclasm". *Gesta* 34, no.

Reference: Barber, Charles. "From Image into Word: The Byzantine Iconoclasts." *Scottish Journal of Theology* 48, no. 1 (1995): 5-10. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.2307/767119>.

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

Are sacred site oriented to environmental features:

"Environmental features" refers to features in the landscape, mountains, rivers, cardinal directions etc...

– Yes

Notes: It should be noted that during the period under investigation one of the most important sacred sites of the Eastern Church was created, Mount Athos. In 963 CE St. Athanasios of Athos thanks to funding from the emperor Nikephoros II Phokas built the first monastery on the peninsula, the Great Lavra, a communal koinobion monastery, the first large one to be built in the Byzantine Empire and a model copied by many subsequent monasteries. Later on, in c. 980 CE Georgian monks founded the Iviron (or Iveron) monastery, which became noted for the production of manuscripts in its scriptorium. Its main church was constructed in 983 CE making it one of the oldest original structures on Mount Athos still intact. By the 11th century CE the holy mountain had 46 monasteries, and besides the Greek and Georgian monks mentioned above, others came from across the Empire and even beyond, including Armenians, Russians, Serbs, Italians, and Bulgarians.

Reference: Speake, Graham, and Kallistos Ware, eds.. *Mount Athos*. Edited by Graham Speake and Kallistos Ware. Peter Lang UK, 2012. <https://doi.org/10.3726/978-3-0353-0233-2>.

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

Notes: Albeit pilgrimage was disrupted, if not actually ended, by the Arab conquest of the Levant by the mid-7th century CE, when the Byzantine army, as well as the Crusaders, reconquered parts of the Middle East in the 10th century CE ensured that pilgrims could still make their journey to the Holy Land. Constantinople, too, was a major attraction to pilgrims from within and outside the Empire's territories. Yet, the Holy Land was considered as the most important and most popular destination for pilgrims, since it was believed that it was the centre of the world. Sites of interest in Jerusalem included the site of the Resurrection, Gethsemane, the church of Holy Wisdom where Christ was condemned, the birthplace of Saint Mary and her tomb, the cave of the Last Supper, and the tombs of Simeon and James. Moreover, throughout the pilgrimage routes were scattered shrines dedicated to saints, martyrs and men and women who had witnessed Christ's ministry. These were usually furnished with impressive buildings or were part of monasteries that tended the shrines and offered accommodation to the pilgrims. Other important pilgrimage sites during the period under investigation include: the city of Edessa in Syria, where the relics of Apostle Thomas and the prized mandylion, a holy cloth which had the impression of Christ on it, were to be found. Following the city's siege in 944 CE the mandylion was taken to the royal palace in Constantinople; Seleucia in southern Asia Minor with its impressive fortified monasteries; Hierapolis in Syria; Euchaita in central Asia Minor; Myra in south-east Asia Minor; Rome and Thessaloniki, where Saint Demetrius had a massive basilica dedicated to him.

Reference: Foss, Clive. "Pilgrimage in Medieval Asia Minor". *Dumbarton Oaks Papers* 56 (2002): 129-51. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.2307/1291859>.

Reference: Weyl Carr, Annemarie. "Icons and the Object of Pilgrimage in Middle Byzantine

Constantinople". *Dumbarton Oaks Papers* 56 (2002): 75–92.
<https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.2307/1291856>.

Reference: Vikan, Gary . *Byzantine Pilgrimage Art*. Washington: DUMBARTON OAKS BYZANTINE COLLECTION PUBLICATIONS, 1982.

Reference: Taylor, Larissa . *Encyclopedia of Medieval Pilgrimage*. Leiden, Boston: Brill, 2009.

- ↳ How strict is pilgrimage:
 - Field doesn't know

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– No

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

- ↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:
 - No

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:
– Field doesn't know

↳ In cemetery:
– Yes

↳ Family tomb-crypt:
– Yes

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):
– Field doesn't know

↳ Other formal burial type:
– Field doesn't know

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ A supreme high god is present:
– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:
– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:
– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):
– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):
– No

- ↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:
 - No

- ↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:
 - No

- ↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:
 - No

- ↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:
 - Yes

- ↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:
 - No

- ↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:
 - Yes
 - ↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:
 - No

 - ↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:
 - No

 - ↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:
 - Yes

 - ↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:
 - Yes

 - ↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):
 - Yes

- ↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):
– Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):
– Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):
– Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):
– Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:
– Field doesn't know
- ↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
– Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god can reward:
– Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god can punish:
– Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:
– No
- ↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:
– Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:
– No
- ↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:
– No

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:
– No

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:
– No

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:
– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:
– Yes

↳ In dreams:
– Yes

↳ In trance possession:
– No

↳ Through divination practices:
– No

↳ Only through religious specialists:
– No

↳ Only through monarch
– No

↳ Other form of communication with living:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Previously human spirits are present:
– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:
– Yes

- ↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:
 - No
- ↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:
 - No
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
 - No
- ↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:
 - No
- ↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:
 - No
- ↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:
 - No
- ↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:
 - No
- ↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:
 - No
- ↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:
 - Yes
- ↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:
 - No

- ↳ Organized hierarchically:
 - Yes
- ↳ Power of beings is domain specific:
 - No
- ↳ Other organization for pantheon:
 - No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes

- ↳ Honesty / trustworthiness / integrity:
 - Yes
- ↳ Courage (in battle):
 - No
- ↳ Courage (generic):
 - Yes
- ↳ Compassion / empathy / kindness / benevolence:
 - Yes
- ↳ Mercy / forgiveness / tolerance:
 - Yes
- ↳ Generosity / charity:
 - Yes
- ↳ Selflessness / selfless giving:
 - Yes
- ↳ Righteousness / moral rectitude:
 - Yes
- ↳ Ritual purity / ritual adherence / abstention from sources of impurity:
 - Yes
- ↳ Respectfulness / courtesy:
 - Yes
- ↳ Familial obedience / filial piety:
 - Yes
- ↳ Fidelity / loyalty:
 - Yes

- ↳ Cooperation:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Independence / creativity / freedom:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Moderation / frugality:
 - Yes
- ↳ Forbearance / fortitude / patience:
 - Yes
- ↳ Diligence / self-discipline / excellence:
 - Yes
- ↳ Assertiveness / decisiveness / confidence / initiative:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Strength (physical):
 - No
- ↳ Power / status / nobility:
 - No
- ↳ Humility / modesty:
 - Yes
- ↳ Contentment / serenity / equanimity:
 - Yes
- ↳ Joyfulness / enthusiasm / cheerfulness:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Optimism / hope:
 - Yes

- ↳ Gratitude / thankfulness:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reverence / awe / wonder:
 - Yes
- ↳ Faith / belief / trust / devotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ Wisdom / understanding:
 - Yes
- ↳ Discernment / intelligence:
 - Yes
- ↳ Beauty / attractiveness:
 - No
- ↳ Cleanliness (physical) / orderliness:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Other important virtues advocated by the religious group:
 - I don't know

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: This stands for the laity. For the monks, on the other hand, and the bishops (i.e. monks that managed to climb the hierarchy), celibacy and full sexual abstinence was mandatory.

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– Yes

↳ On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Generally, the performance of a ritual in the Eastern Orthodox Church requires the participation of the people. Therefore, the presence of at least one lay person (besides the priest) is necessary for the performance of a sacrament.

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– No

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– No

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– No

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– No

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– No

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– An empire

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– Yes

Notes: The most prominent charitable activity during the period under investigation was alms and food distribution to the people who were in need at the gates of the monasteries. Giving alms and food to the poor had always been a substantial part of the philanthropic activities of the monasteries and had been performed on various occasions. At the end of each day, the left-overs were distributed to the needy and this daily practice of alms-giving was a rule for most of the monasteries. Furthermore, this practice had also been performed during great Christian celebrations like Christmas, Easter, and Pentecost and in special occasions, such as feast day of the patron saint of the monastery and annual commemoration ceremonies of the people who were mentioned in the *typika* (the foundational charters) of the monasteries.

Reference: Jenkins, R. "*byzantine Philanthropy and Social Welfare*". *Demetrios J. Constantelos* 45, no. 1 (January 1970). <https://doi.org/10.2307/2855992>.

Reference: Constantelos, Demetrios . *Byzantine Philanthropy and Social Welfare..* New Jersey: Rutgers University Press, 1968.

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– Yes

Notes: For example, Leo VI (886-912) issued a law concerning the shops of Hagia Sophia. Much of this income was used for philanthropic purposes, including the funeral expenses of the poor and perhaps of strangers who had died while visiting the capital.

Reference: Constantelos, Demetrios . *Byzantine Philanthropy and Social Welfare*. New Brunswick: Rutgers University Press, 1968.

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– Yes

Notes: Homes for the elderly were among the charitable institutions that can be considered as an important component of the philanthropic activities of the monasteries and consequently, the official Church authorities.

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Reference: Miller, Timothy. "Byzantine Philanthropic Institutions and Modern Humanitarianism". *The Review of Faith & International Affairs* 14, no. 1 (2016): 18-25. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1080/15570274.2016.1145475>.

Reference: Gilleard , Chris . "Old Age in Byzantine Society". *Ageing & Society* 27, no. 5 (2007): 623-42. <https://doi.org/DOI:https://doi.org/10.1017/S0144686X07006204>.

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Yes

Reference: Markopoulos, Athanasios . "Education". In *The Oxford Handbook of Byzantine Studies*, 785-95. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2012. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1093/oxfordhb/9780199252466.013.0075>.

Reference: Kalogeras, Nikos . "Locating Young Students in Byzantine Churches: A Chapter on Primary and Secondary Religious Education in Byzantium". In *Religious Education in Pre-modern Europe*, 163-81. *Numen Book Series, Volume 140*. Leiden: Brill, 2012. https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1163/9789004232143_008.

↳ Is formal education restricted to religious professionals:

– Yes

Notes: It seems that the secular education, organized by the state, was clearly separated from the religious education for which the Church held the entire responsibility. The University of Constantinople was under the auspices of the emperor and remained active from the fourth to the fifteenth century. The major subjects taught there were classic literature, science and philosophy, but not theology. The latter was included in the curriculum of the Patriarchic School, probably founded in the seventh century in the Byzantine capital, where attendants were clergymen and theologians. Minor schools educating the monks were located in many monasteries.

↳ Is such education open to both males and females:

– Field doesn't know

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: The milestone for the state higher education in Byzantium is the year 425, when the Emperor Theodosius II, under the influence of his sister, his wife Aelia Eudocia (a pagan and daughter of Leontius, a teacher of rhetoric at the school of Athens) and of the poet and philosopher Cyrus of Panopolis, carried out a thorough reorganization and re-structured the operation of the capital's main institution, the Imperial University of Constantinople, the so-called "Pandidacterium." There is little information about the University from the 6th to the 9th centuries, a time period that is considered as its "dark age". The University continued to operate (in fact, St. Maximus the Confessor studied rhetoric and philosophy there), yet the religious and educational policies of various Emperors made its operation extremely problematic. The end of the iconoclasm, however, marked a new era for the Pandidacterium. At the initiative of Caesar Bardas, the Pandidacterium moved its establishments at the Magnaura Palace. Bardas took care for the teaching staff, as well as for the reorganization of its curriculum, which is now strictly limited to the study of the secular lessons. As the head of the teaching staff of the was appointed Leo the Philosopher or Mathematician, a renowned scholar and a great compiler, who brought together a wide range of philosophical, medical, and astronomic text, while he composed his own medical encyclopaedia and was the first Byzantine scholar to deal with the Platonic work itself, correcting the text of the Laws up to the 5th book, which is included in the most ancient Platonic manuscript (Parisinus graecus 1807). Patriarch Photius also taught grammar, rhetoric and philosophy at the Pandidacterium, as well as Arethas of Patras, later bishop of Caesarea (to whom we owe the great codex of the Platonic work Clarkianus 39, at the Bodleian library in Oxford). The emperors of the Macedonian Dynasty took care for the Pandidacterium, especially Constantine VII the Porphyrogenitus (or the Scholar Emperor). The Pandidakterion was refounded in 1046 by Constantine IX Monomachos who created the departments of Law and the Department of Philosophy, where Michael Psellus served as its director.

Reference: Cavallo, Guglielm. *Lire À Byzance*. Paris: Belles lettres, 2006.

Reference: Constantinides, Constantinos. *Higher Education in Byzantium in the Thirteenth and Early Fourteenth Centuries, 1204-ca.1310*. Nicosia: Cyprus Research Centre, 1982.

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Reference: Wolska-Conus, Wanda. "Les Écoles De Psellos Et De Xiphilin Sous Constantin IX

Monomaque". *Travaux Et Mémoires* 6 (1976): 223–43.

Is extra-religious education open to both males and females:

– Field doesn't know

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– Field doesn't know

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– Field doesn't know

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– No

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– Yes

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– Yes

Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– No

Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– Yes

Notes: St. Ignatius had been appointed to his position by the Empress Theodora and out of loyalty to her, refused to give his consent for her exile, ordered by her brother, Bardas. Hence, St. Ignatius was put on trial and exiled to Sedef Island in the Sea of Marmara in July 857.

Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Field doesn't know

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– Yes

Notes: For example, some supporters of St. Ignatius organized a plot to murder Bardas. But they were uncovered and beheaded in the Hippodrome. After that incident, a certain person called Gebeon claimed that he was Theodora's son and the rightful king. Many partisans of St. Ignatius supported him. He was put on trial, and St. Ignatius undertook his defense. He lost the case and Gebeon was executed.

Reference: Dvornik, Francis . The Photian Schism. History and Legend. Cambridge : Cambridge University Press, 1948. <http://macedonia.kroraina.com/en/fdps/index.htm>.

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– Yes

Notes: In his attempt to consolidate power, Bardas accused the Empress Theodora of intrigue and, as it was thought inappropriate to kill members of the imperial family, exiled her to a monastery.

Reference: Dvornik, Francis . The Photian Schism. History and Legend. Cambridge : Cambridge University Press, 1948. <http://macedonia.kroraina.com/en/fdps/index.htm>.

Reference: Runciman, Steven . The Byzantine Theocracy. Cambridge : Cambridge University Press, 1977. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9780511562334>.

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: In fact, Basil I, the founder of the Macedonian dynasty, ordered lawyers to reexamine the Justinian code in order to abridge it, to cast out obsolescent, conflicting, and superfluous items, and to arrange the resultant provisions into orderly single titles. Basil's jurists produced 40 books, which were enlarged to 60 under his son and heir to the throne, Leo. The "Basilica" as the new law code was named, was written in Greek and was a collection of canon law, as well as of civil and public law. It was far more systematically arranged than Justinian's code. The Basilica became the foundation of Byzantine jurisprudence.

Reference: Lawson,, F.H.. "the Basilika". *The Law Quarterly Review* 46 (1933): 486-501.

Reference: Sherman, Charles. "the Basilika. A Ninth Century Roman Law Code Which Became the First Civil Code of Modern Law a Thousand Years Later". *University of Pennsylvania Law Review and American Law Register* 66 (1918): 363-67.

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Reference: Chatzelis, Georgios . "Stratagems and the Byzantine Culture of War: The Theory of Military Trickery and Ethics in Byzantium (c. 900-1204)". *Byzantinische Zeitschrift* 115, no. 3 (2022): 719-68. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1515/bz-2022-0041>.

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Yes

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

- Gathering
- Hunting (including marine animals)
- Fishing
- Pastoralism
- Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Please characterize the forms/levels of food production [choose all that apply]:

- Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

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